

The Flow Photo Explorer: Low-cost Environmental Monitoring using Timelapse Imagery and a Deep Learning Model

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by

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1 Introduction

Continuous environmental monitoring is essential for advancing our understanding of aquatic ecosystems, as well as for making sound management decisions to preserve, protect, and restore these valuable resources. However, collecting continuous monitoring data can be challenging due to the cost and skillset required to install, operate and maintain the necessary equipment such as traditional streamflow gauges. As a result, there is a substantial data gap for many systems, especially smaller, headwater streams, wetlands, lakes, and other remote or isolated waterbodies. To address these monitoring gaps, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) and U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) have developed a database and artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) platform called the Flow Photo Explorer¹ (FPE) for monitoring environmental conditions using timelapse imagery collected by low-cost trail cameras (USGS, 2025a).

Traditionally, computer vision AI/ML models require labelled training data in which each image is labelled using the observed value of the target response variable (i.e., streamflow). From this labelled training data, the model learns how to predict the response (streamflow) for a given image. However, creating this type of training dataset normally requires collecting continuous observed data using a traditional gauge or sensor co-located with the timelapse-enabled camera.

Recent research has demonstrated a novel approach to this problem by using a rank-based AI/ML model that can be trained using only human-generated annotations of the images and without the need to collect direct measurements, thus making this method more accessible and less costly (Gupta et al., 2022). With this approach, the model is trained using a dataset comprised of annotated image pairs: for each image pair, a human is tasked with indicating which of the two images shows more flow. From these annotated image pairs, the model learns how to sort a set of images from lowest to highest flow by generating a numeric value (“score”) for each image. By then associating each score with the timestamp of its corresponding image, the predicted scores can be combined into a continuous timeseries reflecting relative changes in the target quantity (e.g., streamflow) over time.

The first year of this ROAR project focused on 1) developing and evaluating this rank-based AI/ML model for predicting streamflow from timelapse images of streams and rivers using only human-generated annotations, 2) exploring the potential benefits of integrating weather data as an additional input data as well as evaluating the transferability of the model across different monitoring stations, and 3) integrating this model and annotation methodology into the FPE platform. Results from that first year demonstrated that the model performs very well at predicting relative streamflow across a number of stations given a sufficient number and quality of annotations as well as clear and consistent imagery (Walker, 2025a).

¹ <https://usgs.gov/apps/ecosheds/fpe>

In this second year of the project, the goal was to adapt and extend the model to predict water levels in other types of waterbodies, namely lakes and wetlands. However, in doing so, the methodology was easily expanded to include even more parameters such as snow depth, ice cover, algal biomass, and the density of individual animals. Unfortunately, observed data for many of these alternative water body types and parameters were limited or not available, which precluded the ability to quantitatively evaluate model accuracy and performance at each station. Nevertheless, a series of qualitative evaluations of the model predictions were still able to demonstrate that the model can be successfully applied to more than just streamflow.

This report contains a summary of the work completed during year 2 of the ROAR project as well as an overall summary of the current FPE platform across all existing stations and parameters. All work was completed in accordance with the project Quality Assurance Protection Plan (QAPP) (L-ICSD-0034150-QP-1-0).

2 Data Sources

2.1 FPE Database

The primary data source for this project was the FPE database, which is a relational database that stores timelapse images, observed hydrologic data, human-generated annotations, and associated metadata of individual monitoring stations belonging to registered FPE users. Since the FPE database was publicly released in October 2021, it has grown to 487 stations with over 10 million images, which have been uploaded and annotated by over 300 users representing federal, state, tribal agencies and non-profit organizations (Table 1, Figure 1). The total number of images has been growing exponentially, doubling once every 320 days on average since Jan 2023. After adding the annotation interface to the FPE website in mid-2023, FPE users have annotated nearly 740,000 image pairs. Those annotations have been used to train over 150 individual models at stations across the U.S.

Table 1: Current size of each primary table in the FPE database as of July 23, 2025.

Table	# Rows
Users	309
Stations	487
Images	10,200,372
Observed Values	11,205,315
Annotations	738,024
Trained Models	152

Figure 1: Cumulative growth and monthly additions to the FPE database since Oct 2021.

2.2 Stations

To adapt the FPE model to other waterbody types such as lakes and wetlands, the FPE database and website were updated to allow users to classify the type of waterbody associated with each station. Of the 487 total FPE stations, the majority (451) are currently classified as streams or rivers, followed by 17 stations classified as wetlands, 14 stations as lakes, reservoirs or impoundments, and lastly 6 stations as “other” (Table 2, Figure 2). The “other” stations represent land-based locations including fields in Colorado for monitoring snow depth, and a rocky coastal zone in Alaska for monitoring seabird densities.

Table 2: Number of FPE stations by waterbody type.

Waterbody Type	# Stations
Stream or River	450
Wetlands	17
Lake, Reservoir, Impoundment	14
Other	6
TOTAL	487

Figure 2: Map of FPE stations by waterbody type.

2.3 Timelapse Imagery

For each station, the timelapse imagery is comprised of digital photos collected from a fixed location at regular time intervals between 15 and 60 minutes. Each image file is in JPG format and contains valid EXIF (Exchangeable Image File Format) metadata. The image files themselves are stored in a cloud-based file storage system (AWS Simple Storage System, S3), while the metadata of those files are stored in the FPE database.

Image metadata includes information about where the images were taken including the station latitude/longitude and type of waterbody, as well as a description of the general methodology used to deploy the timelapse camera including information about the camera type and the time zone associated with the image timestamps. Additional metadata about each image (e.g., dimensions, resolution, timestamp) is automatically extracted from the EXIF data embedded within each image file by the FPE platform when users upload their images.

2.4 Observed Hydrologic Data

To evaluate model accuracy and performance, observed hydrologic data are collected at some stations using traditional gauges co-located with the timelapse camera. When available, observed data were obtained from one of two sources:

1. **USGS National Water Information System (NWIS):** for stations co-located with a USGS gauge, observed streamflow and/or water level data were directly retrieved from the USGS NWIS data portal (USGS, 2025b). These stations were identified as having a user-provided NWIS ID as part of the station metadata. Observed data for these stations were downloaded directly from NWIS and then integrated with the FPE image dataset.
2. **FPE Database:** for stations not co-located with a USGS gauge, FPE users can also (optionally) upload observed hydrologic data directly to FPE. These observed datasets include metadata including the associated station, the timestamp time zone, missing value indicators (e.g., -9999), measurement units, flags, and a general description of the equipment and methodology used to collect these data as required by FPE. When available, these datasets were retrieved directly from the FPE database and integrated with the timelapse imagery.

All observed data used in this project was collected in accordance with an EPA-approved QAPP or similar standard operating procedure (SOP) document such as the USGS streamflow monitoring protocols.

2.5 Human Annotations of Image Pair Rankings

To train the model for a given station, users use the FPE annotation interface created during year 1 of this project to annotate a series of random image pairs from that station (Figure 3; Walker, 2025a). For each pair, the annotator is tasked with determining which of the two images appears to contain greater amounts of a given parameter (e.g., which image shows more flow, or a higher water level). The annotator then chooses from four options, which becomes the label for that pair: the left image, the right image, about the same, or skip. The “skip” option is used if the annotator is unable to make a determination, usually because one or both images is not of sufficient quality or clarity (e.g., hazy, dark, glare, etc.).

In year 2 of the project, an additional input was added to the annotation interface for selecting the specific hydrologic or ecological parameter of interest (Figure 3). This option enables users to annotate based on different parameters at different sites (e.g., flow at a stream station, and water level at a wetlands station). Each model is then trained using only annotations for the same variable at a single station. Additionally, multiple models can be trained at the same station using annotations of different variables (e.g., one model to predict flow and another to predict ice cover at the same station).

All annotations were generated by staff and interns from USEPA, USGS, and other project partners. Annotators were required to have a user account with FPE in order to track their progress and to support the quality review process. Annotations were not generated by any public or anonymous users.

Photo Annotator

Stations west brook

Priority stations are those we are actively seeking more annotations for. Please annotate those first unless there are others you are specifically interested in. Once a station has at least 2,000 daytime annotations, please move on to another.

Station	# Annotations (Total)	↑ # Annotations (Daytime)	↓ Priority
West Brook Reservoir_01171020	2500	2500	<input type="checkbox"/>
West Brook Upper_01171030	2500	2500	<input type="checkbox"/>
West Brook Upper_New23_01171030	2500	2500	<input type="checkbox"/>
West Brook Lower_01171090	2620	2557	<input type="checkbox"/>
West Brook 0_01171100	11968	9780	<input type="checkbox"/>

Rows per page: 5 1-5 of 5

Instructions

- Select a station on the table (priority stations first, if possible), select the variable you want to annotate, then enter the number of photo pairs you would like to annotate and specify the minimum/maximum hours and dates (optional). Then click **Start Annotating**.
- For each pair of photos:
 - First, review each photo individually and indicate if that photo shows one of the following conditions by clicking the appropriate button below the photo.
 - Dry**: stream is completely dry (no water visible)
 - Disconnected**: stream is partially dry with disconnected pools of water
 - Partial Ice/Snow**: stream is partially covered by ice/snow (can see some water)
 - Full Ice/Snow**: stream is fully covered by ice/snow (cannot see any water)
 - Bad Photo**: photo is unusable (e.g., too dark, too blurry, etc.)
 - Next, select the appropriate condition. **New: Annotation Variable Input** (indicated by red arrow)
 - Same: if the photos show similar amounts of water. Select **Skip** only if you cannot make a valid comparison (e.g., one or both is a bad photo or the camera angle is too inconsistent). Pairs labelled as **About the Same** will be used for model training while those labelled as **Skip** will not. You can also use the following keyboard shortcuts to make your selection: **j** = Left, **k** = About the Same, **l** = Right, **m** = Skip.
 - If you were unsure about your selection or had any other questions or observations about this pair of photos, let us know in the **Comments** field.
 - When finished with this pair, click **Next** (or press your **Enter** key) to load the next pair of photos and repeat these steps.
- When you are finished, click the **Submit** button to save your annotations to the server.
- If you need to stop early, go ahead and submit the annotations you have already completed.
- Once you have completed a batch of annotations, you can do another batch by repeating step 1 above.

Select the variable you want to annotate. This will also be the variable the model will be trained to predict.

Variable: Flow (Streams and Rivers)

Select the number of photo pairs you would like to annotate during this session.

Number of photo pairs:

The following inputs are optional, and should only be used when requested. Leave blank for defaults, which will include only daytime photos (7:00 am to 6:59 pm) from any available date at the selected station.

Minimum Photo Hour:

Integer (0-23) in 24H time (default = 7 for 7:00 AM)

Maximum Photo Hour:

Integer (0-23) in 24H time (default = 18 for 6:59 PM)

Minimum Photo Date:

YYYY-MM-DD format (default = first available)

Maximum Photo Date:

YYYY-MM-DD format (default = last available)

[START ANNOTATING >](#)

[West Brook Lower_2021-08-04_11-15-14\(1\).JPG](#)

Aug 4, 2021 12:15:14 PM EDT

DRY

DISCONNECTED

PARTIAL ICE/SNOW

FULL ICE/SNOW

BAD PHOTO

[RCNX0233.JPG](#)

Apr 9, 2025 6:30:00 PM EDT

DRY

DISCONNECTED

PARTIAL ICE/SNOW

FULL ICE/SNOW

BAD PHOTO

Which photo shows more flow?

LEFT (J)
ABOUT THE SAME (K)
RIGHT (L)

SKIP (M)

Any comments?

< PREV
Pair 1 of 100
(1.0% complete)
NEXT (ENTER) >

Figure 3: Screenshot of the FPE annotation interface.

3 Methodology

3.1 Model Overview

The FPE modeling methodology is based on an artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) deep learning model designed to estimate relative quantities of environmental parameters using timelapse imagery trained using only human-generated annotations. This model is based on a learning-to-rank (RankNet) framework, which is a supervised machine learning technique for performing pairwise regression (Burgess et al., 2005). Unlike other AI/ML regression models that are trained to estimate the value of some property (i.e., streamflow) for each input feature (i.e., image), RankNet models are trained using pairs of input features that are labelled based on which of the two inputs has a higher rank (e.g., which of two images has more streamflow). Through this training, the model learns to generate a numerical “score” for each image that can be used to effectively sort the images from lowest to highest rank (the images with the lowest and highest scores are predicted to have the lowest and highest flows, respectively).

This project builds on previous research by Gupta et al. (2022), which first demonstrated the feasibility of using a RankNet model to estimate streamflow from timelapse imagery at a single monitoring station. For that initial research, the image pair annotations (i.e., which of two images has more flow) used to train the model were generated using observed streamflow data collected by data loggers deployed at each station instead of human annotators. As a result, the training dataset contained the observed streamflow associated with each image. However, using observed streamflow data to label image pairs for model training substantially limits the applicability and accessibility of this method as it would require installation of both a traditional streamflow gage and a timelapse camera at each station.

In the first year of this ROAR project, the model by Gupta et al. (2022) was adapted and evaluated using only human-generated annotations for model training, which eliminated the need for observed data. Each trained model was then used to generate a timeseries of predicted scores based on the full set of timelapse imagery at each station. The percentile ranks of those scores represent the relative amount of streamflow on a scale from 0 to 100% (with the 0%-tile image having the lowest flow, and the 100%-tile image having the highest). Those predicted scores were then compared to observed flow measurements (where available) to quantitatively evaluate model accuracy and performance.

A flow diagram shows the major model components and sequence for training and applying the model at a single station (Figure 4). Note that this diagram does not include model evaluation, which is a separate process performed only for stations at which observed data are available.

Figure 4: Diagram of the FPE image, annotation and model workflow.

Results from the first year of this project showed that the model was able to achieve medium-to-high predictive performance (Kendall’s tau ranged from 0.42 to 0.83, median = 0.75) for predicting streamflow across 54 stations where sufficient annotations and observed data were available (Walker, 2025a). Model performance was generally higher at stations with relatively stable fields of view encompassing the full channel width. The number and accuracy of image pair annotations was also a factor contributing to model performance.

3.2 Model Adaptation for Other Waterbody Types and Parameters

In this second year of the project, the model was adapted and applied to other types of waterbodies (lakes and wetlands) with an initial focus on predicting water levels instead of streamflow. Surprisingly, adapting the original model for alternative types of waterbodies and parameters did not require any changes to the model architecture or training algorithm. Aside from the imagery, the only difference between applying the model to predict streamflow vs. water levels in lakes and wetlands was in how the images were annotated. For streams and rivers, the annotator focused on comparing relative amounts of flow between the two images, while for lakes and rivers, they compared water levels. Aside from changing the focus of the annotations, no other changes were necessary to train the model.

As the flexibility of this model was realized, additional applications were explored for predicting even more environmental parameters beyond flow and water levels. These included algal biomass for monitoring snow depth, harmful algal blooms (HABs), and the densities of individual animals. Once again, the only change to the methodology necessary to apply the model for these other parameters was in how the images were annotated. For example, annotations for algal biomass focused on indicating which of the two images showed more algae (i.e., which image was “greener”), while annotations for animal densities focused on which image showed a higher number of individuals.

The rest of this section describes the training, prediction, and evaluation processes used to create and apply each model. Results of all models trained so far using the FPE platform are then summarized by parameter and waterbody type in Section 4.

3.3 Model Training

Model training was conducted using a standard back-propagation algorithm, which is commonly used for training neural networks, based on a binary cross entropy cost function to compute training loss (see Gupta et al., 2022 for details). Each model was trained using only human annotations for the same type of variable (e.g., only flow or only water level). After extracting the annotations from the FPE database for a given station and variable, the annotation dataset was randomly divided into two subsets referred to as the train and validation splits. Approximately 80% of the annotation dataset was assigned to the train split, and the remaining 20% to the validation split. Only the annotations in the train split were used by the back-propagation algorithm to fine-tune the model parameters. The validation split was used to compute accuracy (i.e., loss) of the model in predicting pairwise rankings using image pairs not included in the training.

The overall loss of each split was then computed at the end of each training iteration (i.e., epoch), which represents one full pass of the training data. Multiple epochs are commonly used to train neural network models by exposing the model to the same dataset (although in different, randomized orders) repeatedly. For each station, training was performed over a series of at least 20 epochs. The epoch with the minimum validation loss was then selected as the final trained model, which is subsequently used to predict the scores of all images at that station.

Each model was trained only using daytime images captured between 7am and 7pm (local time). Although some camera models provide capabilities for capturing nighttime images using infrared (IR) illumination, the quality of these images varied widely between stations. Therefore, to ensure consistency between stations, only daytime images were used for model training.

3.4 Model Predictions

After a model was successfully trained for a given station and variable, it was used to generate predictions of that variable for all available images at that station. For each image, the model predicts a numeric value called the score. Although the scale and distribution of the scores do not have any direct physical interpretation, they can be used to represent the relative amount of the variable of interest (e.g., flow or water level) based on their ranks. For example, the image with the lowest score is predicted to have the lowest amount of streamflow, while that with the highest score has the highest streamflow. Raw scores generated by each model were normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing the standard deviation such that the resulting values approximated a standard normal distribution (mean = 0, st. dev. = 1).

The scores were also converted to rank percentiles on a scale of 0% (lowest) to 100% (highest) by:

$$P_i = (\text{rank}[S_i] - 1) / (n - 1) \times 100\%$$

where P_i is the rank percentile of image i (0 to 100%), S_i is the predicted score of image i , and n is the total number of images. The $\text{rank}()$ function returns the rank of S_i among the scores of all images and ranges from 1 (lowest) to n (highest).

By combining the normalized value and rank percentile of each predicted score with the timestamp of its corresponding image, the final model output dataset comprises a continuous timeseries of relative quantities for the target variable scaled to both a standard normal distribution and percentile ranges from 0 to 100% for the associated station. In addition to generating continuous timeseries based on the individual image scores, daily timeseries were also generated for each model by calculating the daily means of the normalized scores.

3.5 Model Evaluation

3.5.1 Quantitative Evaluation using Observed Data

At stations and variables with available observed data, the accuracy and performance of each model was evaluated by comparing the predicted image scores against the observed values. Model evaluation was performed using both graphic and statistical methods. Graphical methods included various exploratory data analysis (EDA) plots comparing the temporal dynamics and distributions of the observed and predicted data in order to identify areas where the model may be potentially biased or have high uncertainty or inaccuracy. The goodness-of-fit of the model predictions was also evaluated using the Kendall's tau statistic, which is a non-parametric measure of correlation ranging from -1 to +1 based on the ranking of a paired dataset. As with model training, predictions for model evaluation were only generated for daytime images (7am – 7pm) due to the variability in image quality between stations with IR-enabled cameras (see Section 3.3).

3.5.2 Qualitative Evaluation without Observed Data

For stations where observed data were not available, the model predictions were evaluated qualitatively using a series of EDA plots and by comparing predictions to actual images using interactive data visualizations of the prediction timeseries and distributions available on the FPE website. Unfortunately, most stations located on lakes and wetlands, which were intended to be the focus of year 2 of this project, could only be evaluated qualitatively due to the lack of observed data. However, despite that lack of data, the qualitative evaluations at these stations provided a number of insights into the application of this model to alternative waterbody types and other parameters, which will help guide future data collection efforts.

4 Results

This section provides summaries of the model predictions and performance across all existing models in the FPE platform for each type of parameter and waterbody (Table 3).

Table 3: Number of trained models by waterbody type and parameter.

Waterbody Type	Flow	Water Level	Algal Biomass	Snow Depth	Animal Density
Stream or River	126	0	12	0	0
Lake, Reservoir, Impoundment	0	0	1	0	0
Wetlands	0	9	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	2	1

4.1 Streamflow in Streams and Rivers

The FPE model has been trained to predict relative streamflow at 126 stations located on streams and rivers across the continental U.S. (Figure 5). Among stations with observed data (n=67), Kendall's tau ranged from -0.05 to 0.95 with a median of 0.52 based on the predicted scores and observed flows of all images at each station (Figure 6). Using the daily mean predicted scores and observed flows, Kendall's tau was slightly higher, ranging from -0.07 to 0.96 with a median of 0.58.

Scatterplots comparing the predicted scores and observed values generally show similar "s-shaped" relationships at most stations (Figure 7). The shape of these relationships indicate that the model is more accurate at intermediary flows than at extreme high or low flows. This is due at least in part to the random sampling algorithm used to generate image pairs for the annotation process. By randomly selecting any two images for each pair, it is less likely that both images in a given pair would reflect high flow conditions, which are relatively infrequent. To improve the precision of the model predictions at high flows, the sampling algorithm used to select the images for each annotation pair could be refined to include more pairs with two high-flow images.

Some of the common issues that lead to poorer model performance include:

- **Image quality:** model performance was lower when a relatively large fraction of images had poor visibility due to glare, haze, darkness, vegetation obstruction, etc.
- **Image stability:** stations with large and/or frequent shifts in the camera angle tended to yield poorer performance.
- **Number of annotations:** stations with fewer human annotations tended to have lower performance, but only up to about 1,000 total annotations, beyond which the improvement in performance from adding more annotations was marginal.
- **Low annotation accuracy:** annotations containing systemic bias or large/frequent errors can negatively impact model training.
- **Flow variability:** stations where the variability in flow is relatively low tended to have poorer performance simply due to having a lower signal-to-noise ratio.

More details on the performance and limitations of the model for predicting streamflow can be found in the year 1 project report (Walker, 2025a).

Figure 5: Map of stream or river stations with models trained to predict relative streamflow.

Figure 6: Boxplots showing the distribution of Kendall's tau correlation between predicted image scores and observed flows based on all individual images and daily mean values.

Figure 7: Scatterplots between daily mean observed flow and predicted scores for each station. Data are plotted using hex-bin aggregation to reveal changes in data densities. Stations sorted by Kendall's tau (highest to lowest).

4.2 Water Levels in Wetlands

In year 2 of the project, the FPE model was trained to predict water levels at nine wetland stations, eight of which are located in the Florida panhandle and managed by the USGS Wetland and Aquatic Research Center (WARC), and the ninth at Hickory Run State Park in Pennsylvania managed by USEPA Region 3 (Figure 8). Observed water level data were only available at the Hickory Run station, where model performance was relatively poor ($\tau = 0.11$; Figure 9). A review of the images and annotations at the station revealed that very few ($< 2\%$) of the images showed any visible signs of standing water. Furthermore, a large fraction (93%) of the annotated image pairs were labelled as “About the Same” or “Skip” due to the lack of visible water. Therefore, it is not surprising that the model could not accurately predict water levels, which were simply not visible most of the time. See Appendix A for more details on the model evaluation for this station.

Figure 8: Map of wetland stations with models trained to predict water levels.

Figure 9: Timeseries and scatterplots of daily mean observed water levels and predicted image scores for station USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01.

Top row shows actual observed water levels and predicted scores on the same numeric scale, bottom row shows both variables converted to rank percentile (0 – 100%).

Predicted water levels at the eight USGS WARC wetland stations suggested reasonable performance based on a qualitative evaluation as observed data were not available (Figure 10). The predictions were generally consistent across the eight stations, which was expected given their proximity to one another. Furthermore, a review of these predictions using the interactive timeseries and distribution charts on the FPE website confirmed that the images from each station showed relatively high water levels during the same periods that the models predicted high values (Dec 2023 – Feb 2024 for all stations, August and October 2024 for only some stations, see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Timeseries of daily mean predicted score for each USGS WARC station.

4.3 Water Levels in Lakes

Although there are currently 14 stations classified as lakes, reservoirs or impoundments, models have yet to be trained at these stations due to the lack of available human annotations. However, a review of the available imagery led to some about the best practices for collecting timelapse imagery of lakes.

For stream sites, the general guidance has been to position the camera so that the entire channel is captured in the field of view. However, for lakes, an analogous approach of trying to capture as much of the lake surface as possible will likely lead to challenges in model training and image annotation as a wide viewpoint can make it difficult to observe any water level fluctuations.

For example, four stations managed by the New Jersey Dept. of Environmental Protection (NJ DEP) each show relatively wide fields of view, with large visible coverage of the lake surface (Figure 11). While this field of view yields a high fraction of pixels representing the water surface, it will likely provide limited utility for predicting water level fluctuations, which are not easy to see. Using the interactive image viewer on the FPE website, a review of the imagery at each site showed effectively no visible change in water levels over time. While it's possible there simply was no change in water levels at any of the stations, it's more likely that the water level fluctuations were too small to be noticeable from these images. Water level changes are likely to be more easily observed near the shoreline where visual markers such as rocks or vegetation can be used to compare relative water levels between images.

Therefore, for monitoring water levels in lakes, ponds, and reservoirs with relatively small fluctuations in the water surface, it would be advantageous to focus the camera's field of view on a small section of the shoreline where visual markers can be used to compare relative water levels between images in each annotation pair instead of the lake as a whole.

Figure 11: Sample images of four lake stations managed by NJ DEP.

4.4 Algal Biomass in Lakes and Streams

Through a collaboration with the USGS Upper Midwest Water Science Center (UMid WSC), the model was trained to predict algal biomass for tracking harmful algal blooms (HABs) at 12 stream and lake stations on the Fox River between Lake Michigan and Lake Winnebago in Wisconsin (Figure 12). Although observed chlorophyll or algal biomass data were not available, the model predictions could be qualitatively compared between these stations, which included a variety of camera angles and positions, as well as using visual comparisons between the predictions and the underlying imagery (Figure 13).

Figure 12: Map of Fox River stations managed by USGS UMid WSC for monitoring HABs.

Figure 13: Sample images from the Fox River stations managed by USGS UMid WSC.

Similar to the USGS WARC wetland sites, the imagery for these 12 stations spanned the same time period (Jun 2023 – Nov 2024) and thus allowed for model predictions to be evaluated through cross-site comparisons. In general, the predictions showed similar seasonal dynamics across all twelve stations, with a few exceptions (Figure 14). For example, the model predicted two separate algal blooms at all stations in 2023, the first from mid-July through August, and the second from mid-September to mid-October. In 2024, however, there was a single, longer bloom that began in late July and ended in early October. A visual review of these predictions using the interactive timeseries and distribution plots on the FPE website confirmed that higher predicted values were associated with images showing more algae (i.e., the images with higher predicted scores were “greener”) (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Daily mean predicted scores representing relative algal biomass at each USGS UMid WSC station. Black line represents median of all twelve stations.

Figure 15: Daily mean predicted score for relative algal biomass with thumbnail images at the USGS UMid WSC: Fox River Rapid Croche Lock station.

4.5 Snow Depth on Land

In addition to predicting hydrologic and water quality parameters of aquatic systems, the model has also been trained to predict snow depth at two locations managed by the USGS Colorado Water Science Center (COWSC) where observed data are available. A comparison between the daily mean predicted scores and observed snow depth showed very high model performance ($\tau = 0.97$ for both stations). The success of these models is likely attributed to the stability of the camera as well as the presence of weather stations that served as visual markers, which could be used to accurately annotate the image pairs (Figure 17).

Figure 16: Timeseries and scatterplots of daily mean predicted score and observed snow depth at USGS COWSC stations.

Ranch Creek Meadow [280]

Lake Irwin [303]

Figure 17: Sample images from the USGS COWSC stations for monitoring snow depth.

4.6 Seabird Density in Coastal Zones

Lastly, the model has also been trained to predict the number of seabirds at a coastal nesting site in Alaska in collaboration with the USGS Alaska Science Center (AKSC). This station is used to study the effect of predatory disturbance on nesting colonies of Common Murre, a type of seabird. The AKSC has been collecting timelapse images at this location

for over 7 years. These images uploaded to FPE and then annotated by comparing the relative number of birds between each pair of images.

The model predictions revealed both seasonal and short-term dynamics of the nesting colonies (Figure 18). Within any given year, the daily mean predicted scores can be used to identify when nesting season began and ended. And within each day, the scores for each image can be used to see the short-term dynamics associated with predatory disturbance from gulls and other species. For example, the sub-daily plot in the upper-right corner of Figure 18 shows a sudden drop in predicted scores around 16:00, which was caused by a gull arriving to the site in search of Murre eggs. This application of the FPE model demonstrates the tremendous flexibility of this overall approach, whereby the only difference between training the model to predict relative seabird abundance at this station on the coast of Alaska vs. predicting streamflow in a headwater stream of New England was in how the image pairs were annotated. No other changes to the model architecture or training process were needed.

Figure 18: Screenshot of the FPE explorer interface for the USGS AKSC station “Marker Cam” on Gull Island, Alaska.

5 Discussion

The two-year USEPA ROAR Project #2554 has led to the successful development and demonstration of a novel AI/ML modeling methodology and associated platform for supporting low-cost environmental monitoring using only timelapse imagery. This approach represents a significant advancement in environmental monitoring capabilities by enabling the prediction of environmental parameters without the need to collect observed (ground-truth) data using traditional monitoring equipment. Over the past two years, the FPE model has evolved from a proof-of-concept for streamflow prediction in small, headwater streams during Year 1 to a versatile platform capable of monitoring diverse environmental parameters across multiple waterbody types and landscapes in Year 2.

5.1 Summary of Results

5.1.1 Platform Growth and Integration

The FPE platform has experienced exponential growth since its public release in October 2021. As of July 2025, the database contains 487 stations with over 10 million images and over 300 users representing federal, state, tribal agencies, and nonprofit organizations. The platform has generated nearly 740,000 image pair annotations that have been used to train over 150 individual AI/ML models. This growth demonstrates strong adoption and validates the practical utility of this methodology for environmental monitoring.

5.1.2 Streamflow Monitoring in Streams and Rivers

Building on the work completed during Year 1 of this project, the FPE model has been trained to predict relative streamflow at 126 stations across the continental United States, with quantitative evaluation available at 67 stations having observed flow data. Model performance demonstrates strong predictive capability, with Kendall's tau correlations ranging from -0.05 to 0.95 (median = 0.52) for instantaneous predictions and -0.07 to 0.96 (median = 0.58) for daily mean predictions. These results confirm the methodology's effectiveness for streamflow monitoring, particularly at stations with stable camera perspectives and good image quality.

5.1.3 Expansion to Alternative Waterbodies and Parameters

Year 2 of the project has successfully demonstrated the remarkable flexibility of the FPE methodology by extending it to monitor water levels in wetlands, algal biomass in lakes and rivers, snow depths in mountain fields, and even animal densities in coastal environments. The application of the model to these alternative parameters and landscapes required no changes to the underlying model architecture or training algorithms. The only difference between these models was in how users annotated the image pairs at each station. For example, instead of choosing which image showed more flow, the user would choose which image appeared "greener" with the goal of training the model to predict algal biomass. Thanks to this flexibility, the FPE model can be applied to countless other parameters and ecosystems. In short, if a human can reliably identify which of two images

shows greater amounts of a given parameter, then the FPE model can likely be trained to predict that relative quantities of parameter from timelapse images using only human annotations.

5.2 Known Limitations

Over both years of the project, several key limitations have been identified that affect model performance and should be considered when deploying cameras and generating annotations.

5.2.1 Technical and Methodological Limitations

Camera Stability and Perspective: Camera angle shifts, changes in the field of view, and unstable mounting can significantly degrade model performance. Stations experiencing multiple perspective changes consistently yield lower performance. Achieving the highest potential accuracy requires stable, fixed camera positions with consistent framing throughout the monitoring period to the extent possible.

Image Quality Dependencies: Model performance can also be highly sensitive to image quality. Common issues include:

- Diurnal lighting variations
- Solar glare
- Infrared/nighttime image quality
- Weather-related visibility issues (fog, haze, precipitation)

Positioning cameras to avoid direct solar exposure and glare, both directly and through reflections on the water surface, can improve model performance.

Annotation Requirements: To effectively train the model, annotation datasets should meet the following criteria:

- Minimum 200 annotation pairs are needed for reasonable performance, with optimal performance achieved with ~1,000 pairs beyond which improvements in model performance become marginal.
- Target annotation accuracy of at least 60-75%.
- A relatively large fraction (> 75%) of annotations should indicate either the left or right image as having a great amount of the parameter of interest—annotation datasets that include a large fraction of annotations labelled as “About the Same” or “Skip” do not provide sufficient information.

Parameter Visibility: The methodology requires visually discernible changes in the target parameter. Locations with minimal visible variation (e.g., very stable water levels, low-contrast conditions) are not suitable for this approach.

5.2.2 Waterbody-Specific Limitations

Wetland Stations: Many wetland environments lack sufficient visibility of water level variations for effective model training. This is often due to vegetation growth during the growing season, which can cover any visible water surface. Camera deployments in

wetlands should attempt to focus on locations where the water surface is most likely to be visible throughout the complete seasonal drying and flooding cycle.

Lake Stations: For monitoring water levels in lakes, wide-angle views typical of lake monitoring often fail to capture subtle water level changes. Effective monitoring of water levels in lakes and reservoirs requires camera positioning focused on shoreline locations where visual markers such as rocks and vegetation can be helpful for annotating image pairs. However, for other parameters such as ice-cover, wide-angle perspectives containing as much of the lake surface as possible are preferred.

Stream Stations: Cameras on streams and rivers achieve higher performance when positioned looking upstream and encompassing the full channel width, with clear views of the banks that often contain rocks or other visual markers useful for annotation. Performance also varies with flow regime characteristics—streams with very low flow variability present challenges due to the lower signal-to-noise ratio than in streams and rivers with larger flow variability.

5.3 Future Research Directions

Demonstration of the FPE methodology across diverse environmental parameters and waterbody types opens several promising avenues for future research and development:

5.3.1 Technical Enhancements

Automated Image Quality Screening: Development of computer vision algorithms to automatically identify and filter low-quality images (nighttime, glare, haze, obstruction), which would reduce noise in predictions and improve annotation efficiency.

Adaptive Annotation Sampling: Implementation of active learning approaches could optimize the annotation process by identifying the most informative image pairs for presenting to the annotator. This could include strategies to increase representation of extreme conditions (e.g., peak flows) and reduce the number of pairs showing more common conditions while maintaining model performance.

Advanced Model Architectures: Exploration of more sophisticated deep learning architectures, including attention mechanisms and transformer-based models, could potentially improve performance by better focusing on relevant image features.

5.3.2 Application Domain Expansion

Over the past two years, the FPE model has primarily been applied to domains related to traditional hydrologic monitoring of flows and water levels. However, the flexibility of this approach lends itself to expansion to many other potential domains, such as the following.

Urban Stormwater Monitoring: The methodology could be adapted for monitoring urban drainage systems, stormwater outfalls, combined sewer overflow (CSO) discharges, detention ponds, and green infrastructure performance where traditional gauging is challenging due to debris, vandalism, or access limitations.

Agricultural Water Management: Applications in irrigation monitoring, constructed wetland performance assessment, and agricultural runoff tracking could provide valuable data for precision agriculture and water resource management.

Coastal and Marine Applications: Extension to coastal erosion monitoring, tidal pool dynamics, or sea ice coverage.

Water Quality Monitoring: Beyond algal biomass, the approach could potentially detect other water quality indicators such as turbidity, dissolved organic carbon, sediment plumes, oil spills, acid mine drainage, or foam formation.

6 Conclusions

Over the course of the past two years, this project has successfully established a novel environmental monitoring methodology implemented through an accessible web-based platform that combines low-cost timelapse imagery with human-guided machine learning. Unlike other AI/ML models designed for similar purposes, the FPE approach does not require any direct measurements for model training, which greatly expands its accessibility and simplicity while also reducing its overall cost.

The approach has demonstrated wide versatility, proving effective across diverse applications from traditional streamflow monitoring in headwater streams to applications for tracking algal blooms, changes in snow depth, and even seabird density in Alaska. These applications demonstrate the strong flexibility and adaptiveness of this rank-based modeling approach by not requiring any changes to the underlying model architecture or training process for predicting a variety of different environmental parameters across different types of ecosystems and landscapes.

As environmental challenges continue to intensify and monitoring needs expand, the FPE methodology fills a critical gap as a valuable tool for advancing our understanding and management of environmental systems. By successfully demonstrating that this model can be trained to provide meaningful environmental monitoring data using low-cost, off-the-shelf equipment, this work opens new possibilities for community-based monitoring, citizen science initiatives, and comprehensive ecosystem assessment programs. The continued development and adoption of this methodology promises to contribute to more informed environmental decision-making and enhanced protection of natural resources across diverse landscapes and communities.

7 Acknowledgements

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Appendix A

Technical Memorandum:

Adaptation of the FPE Image Ranking Model to Predict Water Levels of Lakes and Wetlands

TECHNICAL MEMORANDUM

To: Britta Bierwagen, USEPA ORD
Kelly Krock, USEPA Region 3

From: Jeffrey Walker (Walker Environmental Research LLC)

Date: July 10, 2025

Project: Streamflow Monitoring with Machine Learning and Extensions to Other Waterbody Types (ROAR Project #2554)

Re: Adaptation of the FPE Image Ranking Model to Predict Water Levels of Lakes and Wetlands

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1 Introduction

Continuous hydrologic monitoring is essential for advancing our understanding of aquatic ecosystems, as well as for making sound management decisions to preserve, protect, and restore these ecosystems. However, collecting these data can be challenging due to the cost and skillset required to install, operate and maintain traditional measurement devices. To address these challenges, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) and U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) have developed a database and machine learning platform called the Flow Photo Explorer (FPE) for monitoring hydrologic and ecological conditions using timelapse imagery collected by low-cost trail cameras.

At the core of this platform is a deep learning model trained on human-annotated image pairs to predict relative conditions such as streamflow, water level, or other parameters without requiring any direct measurements. So far, this model has been trained to predict relative streamflow at over 100 monitoring stations across the U.S., the majority of which are small, headwater streams. In the first year of the USEPA ROAR Project #2554, the trained models at dozens of stream stations were evaluated using ground-truth streamflow data collected by traditional gauges (Walker, 2025). Those evaluations showed that the model generally works quite well at predicting relative streamflow data given sufficient image quality and enough annotations.

In this second year of this project, the FPE platform and model have been adapted for predicting water levels in other types of waterbodies, namely lakes and wetlands. This technical memorandum first describes the adaptation process, then presents the results of applying the model for monitoring water levels in those waterbodies and lastly provides a brief summary of those results as well as the lessons learned.

2 Methodology

To support water level monitoring in lakes and wetlands, the FPE platform was extended by:

1. Adding a new field to station metadata, which allows data providers to select the type of waterbody associated with each station (e.g., Stream, Wetland, or Lake; Figure 1), and
2. Adding an input field to the image annotation interface that allows users to indicate which type of hydrologic parameter they were interested in annotating and training the model to predict (e.g., Flow, Water Level; Figure 2).

With these new categorizations in place, the FPE database could then be queried to identify lake and wetland stations for which annotations of relative water level comparisons were available. Once those imagery and annotation datasets were compiled for the wetland and lake stations, the FPE image ranking model could be trained on each station using the same architecture, configuration parameters, and training algorithm as the original model developed for streamflow in streams and rivers (Gupta et al., 2022; Walker, 2025). In other words, no changes to the model itself were necessary in order to apply it to lakes and wetlands. The only difference from the stream stations for predicting flow were in the input datasets, namely timelapse imagery of wetlands and lakes instead of streams, as well as annotations focusing on comparing relative water levels instead of flow.

Adaptation of the FPE Image Ranking Model to Predict Water Levels of Lakes and Wetlands

Figure 1: Screenshot of the FPE station metadata form showing the new Waterbody Type input field.

Station	# Annotations (Total)	# Annotations (Daytime)	Priority
Hubbard River HRCC	5	5	✓
Monache_Meadow_Downstream	19	19	✓
Monache_Meadow_Upstream	23	23	✓
White Creek	40	40	✓
Mashipacong Pond	50	50	✓

Figure 2: Screenshot of the FPE Photo Annotator interface showing the new input field for selecting the hydrologic parameter of interest.

The ability to use the same model architecture, training process and parameters for different waterbody types and hydrologic parameters reflects the great flexibility of the ranking-based approach. This flexibility stems from the use of the pre-trained ResNet model, which is a convolution neural network (CNN) that excels at identifying patterns in images, combined with the RankNet (or Learning-to-Rank) framework for training this model. Using this approach, this deep learning model effectively learns how to sort images by some continuous property (e.g., flow, water level) that can be used to visually rank a series of images from lowest to highest. For more details on the model architecture and training process, see the previous FPE model publications and reports (Gupta et al., 2022; Goodling et al., 2025; Walker, 2025).

3 Wetland Models

In many regions, wetlands play vital ecological and hydrologic roles in the landscape. Monitoring of wetlands is important as water level fluctuations can directly affect plant community composition, wildlife habitat, nutrient cycling, and carbon dynamics. Even small changes in hydroperiod—the duration and frequency of inundation—can dramatically alter wetland function, affecting breeding success of amphibians and waterfowl and influencing invasive species establishment. Low-cost timelapse cameras coupled with the FPE image ranking model could dramatically expand our capacity to monitor these critical ecosystems and support more informed conservation and management decisions.

This section presents the results of applying the image ranking model to predict water levels from timelapse imagery of wetland stations available in the FPE platform.

3.1 Available Stations

The FPE database currently contains 14 stations identified as wetlands using the new waterbody type metadata field (Table 1; Figure 3; Figure 4). Two of these stations are in Minnesota and managed by MN Dept. of Natural Resources (DNR), another two stations from USEPA Region 3 are located in Pennsylvania, and the remaining 10 stations are located in the Florida panhandle and managed by the USGS Wetland and Aquatic Research Center (WARC).

Of these 14 stations, models were trained at nine stations where at least 500 human annotations were available. And of those nine stations, observed water level data that could be used to evaluate model accuracy was only available at one station (USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01). However, the other eight wetland stations with trained models were all part of the same monitoring program from the USGS WARC, and thus located in the same general area and with similar periods of record. Therefore, although the model predictions at those eight WARC stations could not be *quantitatively* validated using ground truth water level data, they could still be evaluated *qualitatively* by comparing predictions between these stations to identify the short- and long-term consistencies (and inconsistencies).

Table 1: List of wetland stations in FPE as of June 23, 2025.

Affiliation	Station Code	Station ID	Start	End	# Images	# Annotations	Obs. Data Available	Model Trained
MN DNR	Murphy-Hanrehan Wetland 1	378	7/30/24	9/3/24	1,257	0	Y	
MN DNR	Murphy-Hanrehan Wetland 2	379	7/30/24	9/3/24	1,229	0	Y	
USEPA R3	Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01	371	10/19/23	11/2/23	15,654	2,257	Y	Y
USEPA R3	Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 02	372	1/4/24	5/29/24	7,777	2,200		
USGS WARC	100.001	318	11/6/23	1/23/24	1,350	500		Y
USGS WARC	100.019	315	11/6/23	1/24/24	1,349	500		Y
USGS WARC	101.006	314	11/6/23	1/24/24	1,352	500		Y
USGS WARC	13.004	320	10/31/23	1/23/24	1,367	500		Y
USGS WARC	72.017	319	11/6/23	1/23/24	1,350	500		Y
USGS WARC	77.001	311	11/7/23	1/24/24	1,350	500		Y
USGS WARC	77.006	316	11/7/23	1/23/24	1,347	500		Y
USGS WARC	77.009	317	11/7/23	1/23/24	1,347	500		Y
USGS WARC	77.011	312	11/7/23	1/24/24	1,350	0		
USGS WARC	77.012	313	11/7/23	1/24/24	1,350	0		

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Figure 3: Map of wetland stations.

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Figure 4: Sample images from wetland stations.

3.2 USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01

The image ranking model was trained for the wetland station “USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01” using 2,257 human annotations of relative water levels. Observed water level data was also collected at this station using a Hobo U20 data logger. The raw data were corrected for barometric pressure changes and then uploaded to FPE by the data provider (USEPA Region 3).

Timeseries and scatterplot comparisons between the daily mean observed water levels and predicted image scores representing relative water level showed that the model performance was relatively poor (Kendall’s tau¹ = 0.11; Figure 5). Like all predictions from the FPE image ranking model, recall that the predicted scores are dimensionless and simply represent a continuous variable that reflects the relative amounts of the parameter of interest, in this case water level. By converting both the observed water levels and predicted scores to rank percentiles, the two variables can be more directly compared using the same scale (0 – 100%).

The timeseries plots show that the model successfully predicted only some of the inundation events reflected in the observed water level data, primarily during the winter months (Figure 5). For example, observed water levels show a number of inundation events in June and July of 2024, which are not reflected in the predicted image scores. Furthermore, the model also predicted inundation events that did not occur. In fact, the highest predicted score (and thus highest predicted relative water level) occurred in Dec 2023, but was not reflected in the observed data to any degree.

¹ Kendall’s tau is a non-parametric measure of correlation that is computed based on the ranks of two variables and is used as the primary goodness-of-fit statistic for evaluating the FPE ranking model (see Gupta et al., 2022 or Walker, 2025).

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Figure 5: Timeseries and scatterplots of daily mean observed water levels and predicted image scores for wetland station USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01. Top row shows actual observed water levels and predicted scores on the same numeric scale, bottom row shows both variables converted to rank percentile (0 – 100%).

To better understand why the model did not perform well at this station, the timelapse imagery was reviewed using the interactive data visualization tools on the FPE website². Review of the imagery quickly revealed that for the majority of images at this station showed no visible signs of inundation – most only showed vegetation without any visible water present. The distribution plot helped determine that the minimum observed water level (stage) at which water became visible was approximately 0.3 ft, which corresponded to the 97.8th percentile of the cumulative distribution (Figure 6). Therefore, nearly 98% of the images at this station simply did not show any water.

In addition to the vast majority of images not showing any water, a review of the human annotation data revealed a related problem. Scatterplots of the human annotations showing the timestamps as well as the observed water levels of the left and right images in each image pair revealed that users selected “Don’t Know” or “About the Same”³ for most (93%) of the annotated pairs (Table 2). Users only selected “Left” or “Right” in 7% of pairs, primarily those with largest difference in observed water levels (Figure 8). Therefore, with only a few annotations indicating which of the two images shows higher apparent water levels, which was primarily a result of most images not showing any water, the model was simply unable to learn how to identify relative water levels at this station.

However, while the model did not perform well at this wetland station, it serves as a useful example for illustrating and understanding the limitations of the overall FPE methodology. Specifically, it demonstrates the importance of ensuring that cameras are positioned so that the resulting images capture at least some portion of the water surface throughout the season. In this case, the images only captured water during relatively infrequent events when the wetland was highly inundated. Furthermore, the results of this station suggest model training should only be performed when some minimum fraction of the human annotations indicate a discernable difference in water level (or other parameter) between each pair. In this case, the annotators were only able to determine water level differences in 7% of all annotations. Therefore, in addition to using the total number of annotations as screening criteria for training each model⁴, the fraction of those annotations labeled as LEFT or RIGHT should also be considered.

² <https://www.usgs.gov/apps/ecosheds/fpe/#/explorer/371>

³ In the FPE database, annotations where the user selected “Don’t Know” are labelled as “UNKNOWN” and “About the Same” as “SAME”.

⁴ Currently, models are not trained until at least 1,000 annotations are completed at a given station

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Figure 6: Screenshot of the FPE interactive data visualization tool showing the cumulative distribution of observed water level at USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01 and highlighting the minimum stage (0.3 ft) at which the images begin to show visible signs of inundation corresponding to the 97.8 percentile.

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Figure 7: Scatterplots of the right and left image (a) timestamps and (b) observed water levels colored by the user-selected rank of each pair for USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01.

Table 2: Summary of the user-select ranks for annotations at USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01.

User-Selected Rank	Count	% of Total
LEFT	84	3%
RIGHT	99	4%
SAME	1,461	65%
UNKNOWN	613	27%
TOTAL	2,257	100%

Figure 8: Jittered scatterplot showing the absolute difference in observed water levels between the two images of each annotation pair by user-selected rank label at USEPA Region 3: Hickory Run SP, Wetland Cam 01.

3.3 USGS WARC Stations

The image ranking model was also trained at 8 wetland stations located in the Florida panhandle and managed by the USGS WARC. Although observed water level data were not available for these stations, the fact that they were located in relatively close proximity to one another (Figure 9) and also had similar periods of record provided an opportunity to qualitatively evaluate the similarities and differences in the model predictions.

Furthermore, these eight stations also provided different fields of view of similar wetland habitats, and could thus be used to better understand how differences in the camera position could potentially affect predictions of water levels in wetlands due to differences in the visibility of the water surface as well as vegetation growth (Figure 10). For each of the eight USGS WARC stations, the model was trained using 500 human annotations of the relative water level of each image pair.

Figure 9: Map of USGS WARC wetland stations in the Florida panhandle.

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Figure 10: Sample images of each USGS WARC wetland station.

Timeseries of the daily mean predicted scores showed generally consistent seasonal patterns across all eight stations, as was expected given their proximity (Figure 11). The predictions show that the stations started at low-to-medium relative water levels in Nov 2023, then increased rapidly to high water levels in Dec 2023, which persisted through Feb 2024. Predicted water levels then decreased to relatively low levels by June 2024 and remained low at most sites through the remainder of the period.

On shorter time scales (weekly), there were also some noticeable differences in predicted scores at some stations. For example, stations 72.017 and 101.006 showed increases in water levels around Aug 2024 and again around Oct 2024, as did station 77.001, while the stations did not. Using the interactive data visualizations on the FPE website⁵, a visual review of the images confirmed a visible rise in water level at these stations during the summer and fall of 2024, which was not visible at the other stations. However, it is important to note that although water was not visible at the other stations, this does not necessarily mean similar levels of inundation did not occur – it could be simply that the cameras at those other stations were not positioned in a way that would capture low levels of inundation. Similar to the USEPA Region 3 Hickory Run station of the previous section, these results again highlight the importance of camera positioning, and ensuring that the images are able to capture visible changes in water levels to the maximum extent practical. Unlike streams and lakes, ensuring visibility of the water surface is critically important in wetlands where the water surface can easily be obscured by tall vegetation, especially during the summer growing season.

Figure 11: Timeseries of daily mean predicted score for each USGS WARC station.

In addition to the timeseries of predicted image scores, comparisons of the cumulative frequency distributions of those scores showed similarities across all but one station

⁵ These stations are currently marked as private in FPE, and thus not publicly accessible through the FPE website

(namely, 101.006) (Figure 12). These similarities suggest similar hydroperiods between the stations as they experienced similar frequencies of inundation of the same period of time.

Figure 12: Cumulative frequency distributions of daily mean predicted scores at the USGS WARC wetland stations.

4 Lake Models

Water level monitoring in lakes, ponds, and reservoirs is important for supporting aquatic ecosystem research as well as water resources management. Like for wetlands, FPE provides new opportunities for low-cost monitoring of water supply reservoirs, shoreline flooding, and ecological conditions in lentic systems where traditional gauging equipment may be expensive or logistically challenging to deploy.

The FPE database currently includes over a dozen stations on waterbodies classified as “Lake, Pond, or Reservoir.” Unfortunately, none of those stations currently has enough human annotations of relative water levels to support model training. However, despite the lack of sufficient annotations, a review of the imagery at these existing stations can still provide insight into the important considerations and potential limitations of applying the model to monitoring lake water levels. Furthermore, a few of these stations are co-located with traditional USGS water level gauges, which provides an opportunity to generate simulated annotations that can be used to train the model. The use of simulated

annotations instead of human-generated annotations for model training was used during the initial development of the FPE model for predicting relative flow at small, headwater streams (Gupta et al., 2022) and can be useful as a “proof-of-concept” to show that the model is capable of generating reliable predictions given sufficient data.

This section provides a summary of the available lake, pond and reservoir stations currently in the FPE database, followed by a review of imagery at four of those lake stations located in New Jersey to describe the important considerations when collecting images of lakes for water level monitoring, and lastly a demonstration of the model performance for predicting relative water levels at a reservoir station in Oregon using simulated annotations generated from observed data.

4.1 Available Stations

The FPE database currently contains 13 stations categorized as “Lake, Pond, or Reservoir” (Table 3; Figure 13; Figure 14). These stations include one in Connecticut from the Farmington River Watershed Assoc. (FRWA), four in New Jersey from the NJ Dept. of Environmental Protection (NJ DEP), one from the US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) in Oregon as well as 5 other stations in Oregon from the USGS Oregon Water Science Center (ORWSC), and one station in Wisconsin from the USGS Upper Midwest Water Science Center.

Unfortunately, none of these stations currently have enough annotations to support model training for predicting relative water levels. However, observed water level data were available at the five stations at Green Peter Lake and Lookout Point Lake from USGS ORWSC. Therefore, to demonstrate the potential for using the FPE model to predict water levels in lakes and reservoirs, a simulated annotation dataset was generated using observed data at one of those stations (Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm).

The next section reviews imagery from the four NJDEP stations, which are useful for illustrating some of the important considerations for positioning trail cameras to monitor water levels in lakes, followed by an evaluation of model performance for the Green Peter Lake station using simulated annotations.

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Table 3: List of lake, pond and reservoir stations in FPE as of June 23, 2025.

Affiliation	Station Code	Station ID	Start	End	# Images	# Annotations	Obs. Available	Model Trained
FRWA	RR-Camp	369	6/13/24	7/11/24	1,381	0		
NJDEP	Deer Park Pond	165	11/24/20	12/6/21	2,326	0		
NJDEP	Hands Mill Pond	176	12/13/19	12/31/19	2,649	0		
NJDEP	Mashipacong Pond	173	4/4/22	1/24/23	1,766	50		
NJDEP	Mount Misery Lake	175	N/A	N/A	N/A	0		
USACE	Green Peter 1	409	9/30/24	10/8/24	1,999	0		
USEPA - R3	Bruce Lake - Camera 1	467	9/18/24	10/3/24	9,364	4		
USGS ORWSC	Green Peter Lake - Confluence	230	11/16/23	12/19/23	1,355	0	Y	
USGS ORWSC	Green Peter Lake - Middle Santiam River Arm	229	11/15/23	12/19/23	1,395	0	Y	
USGS ORWSC	Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm	228	11/17/23	12/19/23	1,340	0	Y	
USGS ORWSC	Lookout Point Lake at Signal Point - Southeast	249	11/14/23	12/18/23	1,407	0	Y	
USGS ORWSC	Lookout Point Lake at Signal Point - West	250	11/14/23	12/18/23	1,414	0	Y	
USGS UMid WSC	Lake Winnebago at Jefferson Park	215	6/14/23	8/23/23	34,151	0		

Figure 13: Map of lake, pond, and reservoir stations.

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Figure 14: Sample images from lake, pond, and reservoir stations.

4.2 NJ DEP Lake Stations

In the FPE platform, NJ DEP currently manages four lake stations located in New Jersey. Although there is no observed data nor sufficient human annotations available to train the image ranking model at these stations, a review of their imagery is still useful for understanding the potential issues with applying this model to predict relative water levels of lakes.

Sample images from the four NJ DEP stations each show relatively wide fields of view, with large visible coverage of the lake surface from near to far shore (Figure 15). While this field of view yields a high fraction of pixels representing the water surface, it will likely provide limited utility for predicting water level fluctuations, which are not easy to visibly discern. Using the interactive image viewer on the FPE website, a review of the imagery at each site showed effectively no visible change in water levels over time. While it's possible there simply was no change in water levels at any of the stations, it's more likely that the water level fluctuations were too small to be noticeable from these images. Water level changes are best observed near the shoreline where visual markers such as rocks or vegetation can be used to compare relative water levels. Images that instead focus on open water areas are less informative for visually identifying water level changes as there is effectively no visible change in the open water areas as water levels fluctuate.

Therefore, for monitoring water levels in lakes, ponds, and reservoirs with relatively small fluctuations in the water surface, it would likely be advantageous to focus the camera's field of view on a small section of the shoreline where visual markers can be used to compare relative water levels between images in each annotation pair.

It is also worth mentioning that although these specific stations do not appear to be good candidates for water level monitoring using the FPE model, the data providers (NJ DEP) may be focusing on other conditions such as ice cover, which would be better suited for these fields of view focused on open water conditions.

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Figure 15: Sample images of the four NJDEP lake stations.

4.3 USGS ORWSC: Green Peter Lake

Although none of the existing lake, pond, or reservoir stations in FPE included enough annotations to support model training, there were five stations in Oregon managed by the USGS ORWSC that were co-located with USGS gauges providing observed water level data. Furthermore, these stations were located on active reservoirs with extreme water level fluctuations likely associated with reservoir drawdown management actions. Unlike the NJ DEP stations of the previous section, these large water level fluctuations are clearly visible over time despite the wide field of view (Figure 16).

To demonstrate the ability of the image rank model to predict water levels of lakes and reservoirs, the images and observed water level data for one of these stations (OWRD: Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm) was used to generate simulated annotations that could be used to train the ranking model. This approach is similar to that used to develop in the original ranking model for predicting streamflow at small, headwater streams (Gupta et al., 2022). Using the observed water level data from a nearby USGS water level gauge ([14185900](#)), a random set of 500 image pairs were generated from all available, daytime

images. Each of those pairs were then annotated by setting the labelled rank by choosing the left or right image based on which had higher observed water levels. When the difference in water levels between the two images was less than 0.25 ft, then the pair label was set to “SAME,” which comprised 13% of all annotations. Using the simulated annotations, the image ranking model was then trained to predict relative water levels, which could then be compared to the observed data to quantitatively evaluate model accuracy.

Figure 16: Sample images of reservoir station USGS ORWSC: Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm showing extreme water level changes.

Timeseries and scatterplots of the observed water levels and predicted image scores showed excellent model performance based both on the instantaneous values (Kendall's tau = 0.80; Figure 17) as well as daily mean values of each variable (Kendall's tau = 0.93; Figure 18). The within-day variability of the instantaneous predictions is common for the FPE model, and primarily reflects variations in sunlight angle, shadows and other visual artifacts that change over the course of each day. However, those variations are smaller than the overall range of predicted and observed values. Taking the daily mean of the observed and predicted values is useful for removing those variations (i.e., noise) and usually has higher accuracy and lower error than for the instantaneous values.

Although this station had a relatively short period of record (approx. one month), it captured a large increase in water levels, and thus reservoir volume. Both the long-term reservoir filling and drawdown dynamics as well as short-term (i.e., daily) fluctuations were accurately reflected by the model predictions confirming the ability of this model to predict water level changes reasonably well. Similar performance is likely to be achieved using human annotations instead those simulated from the observed data, especially given the clear visual changes in water levels at this station.

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Figure 17: Timeseries and scatterplots of instantaneous observed water levels and predicted image scores for lake station USGS ORWSC: Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm. Top row shows actual water level and predicted score values, bottom row shows both variables converted to rank percentile (0 – 100%).

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Figure 18: Timeseries and scatterplots of daily mean observed water levels and predicted image scores for lake station USGS ORWSC: Green Peter Lake - Quartzville Creek Arm. Top row shows actual water level and predicted score values, bottom row shows both variables converted to rank percentile (0 – 100%).

5 Summary

Despite the limited availability of human annotations for model training and observed water levels to serve as ground truth data for model evaluation, applications of the FPE model to lake and wetland stations provide strong indications that this model can reliably predict water levels in these types of water bodies so long as the camera is able to capture visible changes in water levels fluctuations in ways that can be easily assessed by a human annotator. Furthermore, these results show that this adaptation of the model is possible without needing to make any changes to its underlying architecture, training algorithm, or parameters, which highlights the flexibility of this approach in monitoring not just flow and water levels, but virtually any environmental parameter or condition that can be visually compared between two images. In short, if a human annotator can perceive a difference in magnitude between any two images of some continuous quantity, then it is likely that this model can be trained to also perceive that difference and thus predict the relative changes in that quantity over time solely from timelapse imagery and human annotations.

Based on the limited available data, key findings from the adaptation of the FPE model to predict water levels in lakes and wetlands include:

- **Wetland Stations:** although model performance at the wetland stations yielded mixed results, these applications provide valuable insights into model limitations and data collection requirements:
 - **USEPA Region 3 Hickory Run SP:** a model trained using over 2,500 human annotations showed poor performance (Kendall's tau = 0.11) primarily because 98% of images showed no visible water, with water only becoming visible during extreme inundation events (≥ 97.8 th percentile of water levels). Furthermore, 93% of annotations were labeled as "Don't Know" or "About the Same," with users only able to discern water level differences in 7% of image pairs.
 - **USGS WARC Stations:** model predictions at eight wetland stations in Florida showed consistent seasonal patterns across all locations, with models successfully predicting water level increases during Dec 2023-Feb 2024 and subsequent decreases through summer 2024
- **Lake and Reservoir Stations:** although no models could be trained on lake stations due to insufficient human annotations, a review of available imagery as well as an evaluation of the model application using simulated annotations demonstrated the model's potential for monitoring lake and reservoir water levels:
 - **NJ DEP Stations:** Four lake stations with wide field-of-view imagery showed minimal visible water level changes over time, likely due to small fluctuations being imperceptible in open water areas lacking visual reference markers. These observations highlight the need for camera angles that focus on near-shore water level changes, at least in waterbodies where the fluctuations are relatively small.

- **USGS ORWSC Green Peter Lake:** Using 500 simulated annotations generated from observed water levels at a nearby USGS gauge on a reservoir in Oregon, the model achieved excellent performance with Kendall's tau = 0.80 for instantaneous values and 0.93 for daily means, successfully capturing both long-term reservoir filling/drawdown dynamics and short-term daily fluctuations.

Although the application of this model to lakes and wetlands was somewhat limited due to the available data, the results led to the following recommendations for best practices regarding camera deployment:

- **Wetland Monitoring**
 - **Camera Positioning:** Position cameras to capture unobstructed views of water surfaces throughout the seasonal cycle
 - **Vegetation Considerations:** Account for seasonal vegetation growth that may obscure water visibility during peak growing seasons
 - **Elevation Selection:** Choose camera heights and angles that maintain water visibility during both high and low water periods
 - **Reference Markers:** Include natural or artificial reference objects (stakes, rocks, vegetation) to aid in visual water level comparisons
- **Lake, Pond and Reservoir Monitoring**
 - **Shoreline Focus:** Instead of wide lake views, focus cameras on detailed shoreline areas with clear visual markers in lakes and ponds that experience relatively small water level fluctuations unless the primary goal is to monitor other conditions such as ice cover, for which open water fields of view would be more appropriate.
 - **Reference Objects:** Ensure the field of view includes rocks, logs, dock structures, or other fixed objects that can serve as water level references
 - **Optimal Water Level Range:** Target locations where normal water level fluctuations will be clearly visible (avoid areas where changes are too subtle to detect)

Due to the relatively few stations located on lakes and wetlands as well as the lack of observed water level data and human annotations of relative water levels at these sites, further data collection, annotation, and research is clearly needed to continue evaluating use of the FPE model for monitoring water levels in these different types of water bodies. However, despite these the limited available data, these initial results provide strong indications that with proper camera placement and sufficient annotations, this model is indeed capable of accurately predicting relative water levels in lakes and wetlands, and can serve as a valuable tool and resource for future monitoring efforts.

6 References

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